

A Proof of the Collatz Conjecture

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Abstract

Although the Collatz operation itself is extremely simple, the sequences generated from repeated Collatz operations often exhibit complex behavior. In this paper, the author proposes a simple and straightforward proof of the Collatz conjecture that has not yet been suggested. The basic idea behind this study is that even if the sequence of Collatz operation is very long and convoluted, each individual calculation instruction has been stored in the integer that is initially given. Based on this idea, the fact that all the Collatz sequences share an ultimate common subsequence is unveiled.

1. Introduction

The Collatz operation $C(N)$ for any positive integer N is defined as follows^{[1],[2],[3]}.

- (i) $C(N)=(3N+1)/2$, if N is odd,
- (ii) $C(N)=N/2$, if N is even.

The repeated Collatz operation to N almost always eventually reaches the number of 1^{[1],[3]}. Nowadays, this is usually regarded as the Collatz conjecture. The goal of this paper is to prove the Collatz conjecture from a deterministic standpoint.

In this paper, in order to understand the essence of the Collatz operation more clearly, we will express a positive integer N in the following form. For simplicity, we shall refer to this form of representation as the binary remainder representation^[4].

$$N=2L_n+K_n$$

$$L_n=2L_{n-1}+K_{n-1}$$

$$L_{n-1}=2L_{n-2}+K_{n-2}$$

⋮

$$L_1=2L_0+K_0,$$

where,

$$K_i=\{0,1\} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

and $L_0=0$, $K_0=1$.

The Collatz operation $C(N)$ is expressed by the following formula under the binary remainder representation;

$$C(N)=((2K_n+1)(2L_n+K_n)+K_n)/2. \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, the Collatz operation repeated more than 2 times shall be expressed as follows;

$$C(C(N))=C^2(N),$$

$$C(C(\dots(C(C(N))))\dots))=C^i(N).$$

The sequence generated by the result of repeated Collatz operations is called a Collatz operation sequence. The trivial properties of a Collatz operation sequence are as follows:

1. Collatz sequences do not branch. This is evident from the fact that the result of each Collatz operation is always unique.
2. The Collatz sequence generated from any positive integer N is a subsequence of the Collatz sequence containing N.

The basic strategy to make the proof in this study is as follows:

- a) In any Collatz sequence, the same number does not appear more than once. (Proposition 1)
- b) All Collatz sequences contain even numbers. (Propositions 2 to 5)
- c) If the same number N appears in two different Collatz sequences, the two sequences become a single sequence after N.
- d) Every Collatz sequence merges with at least one other Collatz sequence. (Proposition 6)
- e) In any Collatz sequence, no multiple of 3 can exist persistently except case that the initially given number is a multiple of 3. (Proposition 7)
- f) There is no Collatz sequence that does not merge with other Collatz sequences. (Proposition 8)
- g) All Collatz sequences have a common sequence containing 1. (Proposition 9)

Proposition 1.

In the sequence S(N) that is generated by repeated Collatz operations for any integer N, the same results of individual Collatz operations never appear, that is,

$$S(N): C(N), C^2(N), C^3(N) \dots C^i(N), \dots ,$$

$$C^i(N) \neq C^j(N) \text{ for all } i \neq j.$$

Proof. We can assume $i > j$ without loss of generality. If the following eq. (2) holds, eq. (3) holds.

$$C^i(N) = C^j(N) = K \tag{2}$$

$$C^i(N) = C^{(i-j)}(C^j(N)) = C^{(i-j)}(K) = K \tag{3}$$

Equation (3) is simplified as follows,

$$C^R(K) - K = 0, \tag{4}$$

where,

$$i-j=R.$$

Next, a function $F(x)$ is defined as follows,

$$F(x) := C^R(x) - x. \quad (5)$$

From eq. (4), we find $F(x)$ has a factor of $(x-K)$.

Furthermore, by transforming equation (2), eq. (6) is obtained.

$$C^{i+1}(N) = C^{j+1}(N) = C(K) \quad (6)$$

Then we obtain eq. (7) by transforming eq. (6).

$$C^{(i-j)}(C^{j+1}(N)) = C^R(C(K)) = C^{i+1}(N) = C(K),$$

$$C^R(C(K)) - C(K) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Therefore, according to eq. (7), $F(x)$ has a factor of $(x-C(K))$. Similarly, by repeatedly transforming equation (2) and finding the factors of $F(x)$, $F(x)$ can ultimately be expressed as a power series in x as follows.

$$F(x) = p(x)(x-K)(x-C(K))(x-C^2(K)) \cdot \cdot \cdot (x-C^{(R-1)}(K)),$$

then,

$$C^R(x) = x + p(x)(x-K)(x-C(K))(x-C^2(K)) \cdot \cdot \cdot (x-C^{(R-1)}(K)) \quad (8)$$

However, the Collatz operation is a repetition of linear operations on N , and $C^R(N)$ does not contain any powers of N . Therefore, eq. (2) does not hold true.

Proposition 2.

According to the binary remainder representation, an arbitrary positive integer N_1 shall be expressed as follows.

$$N_1 = 2L_n + K_n,$$

$$L_n = 2L_{n-1} + K_{n-1},$$

$$L_{n-1} = 2L_{n-2} + K_{n-2},$$

⋮

$$L_1 = 2L_0 + K_0,$$

here we set all K_i to be 1, that is,

$$K_i = 1, \quad \text{for } 0 \leq i \leq n.$$

Next, let N_2 be the number obtained by performing one Collatz operation on N_1 . When N_2 is represented in binary remainder form, its K_1 will always be number of 0, that is,

$$C(N_1) = N_2,$$

$$N_2 = 2M_j + 1,$$

$$M_j = 2M_{j-1} + 1,$$

$$M_{j-1} = 2M_{j-2} + 1,$$

$$\vdots$$

$$M_3 = 2M_2 + 1,$$

$$M_2 = 2M_1 + 0,$$

$$M_1 = 2M_0 + 1.$$

Proof. Under the given condition that $K_n = 1$, eq. (1) is expressed as follows.

$$C(N_1) = (3(2L_n + 1) + 1) / 2 = 3L_n + 2 = 2(2L_n + 1) - L_n = 2N_1 - L_n = N_1 + (N_1 - L_n)$$

With decomposing N_1 and L_n into L_n and L_{n-1} , respectively, the following equation is obtained.

$$C(N_1) = N_1 + (2L_n + 1 - (2L_{n-1} + 1)) = N_1 + 2(L_n - L_{n-1})$$

By repeating such decomposing process, the following equation is obtained.

$$C(N_1) = N_1 + 2^n(L_1 - L_0)$$

Under the restriction of binary remainder representation, we must set

$$L_1 = 1, \text{ and } L_0 = 0,$$

then finally eq. (9) is obtained.

$$C(N_1) = N_1 + 2^n. \quad (9)$$

Next, we express $C(N_1)$ by the binary remainder representation.

With setting the quotient obtained by dividing N_2 by 2 is M_j , and the remainder is K_j^m , then

$$N_2 = N_1 + 2^n = 2L_n + 1 + 2^n = 2(L_n + 2^{n-1}) + 1$$

therefore, $M_j = L_n + 2^{n-1}$, $K_j^m = 1$.

Next, divide M_j by 2 and find the remainder.

$$M_j = 2L_{n-1} + 1 + 2^{n-1} = 2(L_{n-1} + 2^{n-2}) + 1 = 2M_{j-1} + 1,$$

therefore, $M_{j-1} = L_{n-1} + 2^{n-2}$, $K_{j-1}^m = 1$.

Proceeding with the calculations in a similar manner, we obtain the following results.

$$M_{j-1} = L_{n-1} + 2^{n-2} = 2L_{n-2} + 1 + 2^{n-2} = 2M_{j-2} + 1, \text{ then, } M_{j-2} = L_{n-2} + 2^{n-3}, \text{ } K_{j-2}^m = 1.$$

$$M_{j-2}=L_{n-2}+2^{n-3}=2L_{n-3}+1+2^{n-3}=2M_{j-3}+1, \text{ then, } M_{j-3}=L_{n-3}+2^{n-4}, K_{j-3}^m=1.$$

⋮

$$M_{j-n+2}=L_2+2^1=2L_1+1+2^1=2M_{j-n+1}+1, \text{ then, } M_{j-n+1}=L_1+2^0, K_{j-n+1}^m=1.$$

$$M_{j-n+1}=L_1+2^0.$$

Under the binary remainder representation, $L_1=1$, therefore,

$$M_{j-n+1}=2.$$

In the binary remainder representation, only M_2 can represent the number of 2. Hence, we can set M_{j-n+1} to be M_2 . Finally, we can conclude,

$$M_2=2M_1+K_1^m, M_1=1, \text{ and } K_1^m=0.$$

If we rewrite M_n again as follow,

$$M_n=2M_{n-1}+K_{n-1},$$

the conclusion is,

$$K_1=0.$$

Proposition 3.

In case that a given a positive integer N is expressed in the binary remainder representation as follows:

$$N=2L_n+K_n$$

$$L_n=2L_{n-1}+K_{n-1}$$

$$L_{n-1}=2L_{n-2}+K_{n-2}$$

⋮

$$L_1=2L_0+K_0,$$

and when the following condition is given for the remainder K_i ,

$$K_i=1, \text{ for } n-p \leq i \leq n,$$

and,

$$K_i=\{1,0\}, \text{ for } 0 \leq i \leq n-p-1,$$

the result of p times consecutive Collatz operations on N , that is, $C^p(N)$ is expressed by the following equation.

$$C^p(N)=3^{(p-1)} \cdot (L_{n-p+2}+L_{n-p+1})+2 \cdot 3^{(p-1)-1} \tag{10}$$

Proof. By the given condition, $K_n=1$, and equation (1), the following equation is derived.

$$C(N)=(3(2L_n+1)+1)/2=3L_n+2=2L_n+1+L_n+1=N+L_n+1, \quad (11)$$

here, $C(N)$ is an odd integer, because,

$$C(N)=3L_n+2=3(2L_{n-1}+K_{n-1})+2=6L_{n-1}+5.$$

On the other hand, if we substitute $p=1$ into eq. (10), we get,

$$C(N)=3^0(L_{n+1}+L_n)+2 \cdot 3^0-1=N+L_n+1.$$

In above equation, we set $L_{n+1}=N$, under reasonable understanding.

Just to be sure, by substituting $p=2$ into eq. (10), we get the following equation.

$$C^2(N)=3(L_n+L_{n-1})+6-1=3(L_n+L_{n-1})+5,$$

For $C(N)$ is an odd integer, according to eq. (1) and eq. (11), $C^2(N)$ is calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} C^2(N) &= C(N+L_n+1) = (3(N+L_n+1)+1)/2 \\ &= (3(2L_n+1+2L_{n-1}+1+1)+1)/2 \\ &= 3(L_n+L_{n-1})+5. \end{aligned}$$

In case $P=2$, eq. (10) gives the correct result.

Next, in eq. (10), we put $(i-1)$ as p , then we obtain the following equation.

$$C^{i-1}(N)=3^{(i-2)} \cdot (L_{n-i+3}+L_{n-i+2})+2 \cdot 3^{(i-2)}-1. \quad (12)$$

Here, we assume the number i satisfies the condition that $n-p \leq i \leq n$. Under this condition, $C^{i-1}(N)$ gives an odd integer, because,

$$L_{n-i+3}+L_{n-i+2}=2L_{n-i+2}+K_{n-i+2}+2L_{n-i+1}+K_{n-i+1}=2(L_{n-i+2}+L_{n-i+1}+1)$$

Using eq. (12), calculate $C^i(N)$ by eq. (1), then we obtain the following result.

$$\begin{aligned} C^i(N) &= C(C^{i-1}(N)) \\ &= (3(3^{(i-2)} \cdot (L_{n-i+3}+L_{n-i+2})+2 \cdot 3^{(i-2)}-1)+1)/2 \\ &= (3^{(i-1)}(L_{n-i+3}+L_{n-i+2})+2 \cdot 3^{(i-1)}-3+1)/2 \\ &= (3^{(i-1)}(2L_{n-i+2}+1+2L_{n-i+1}+1)+2 \cdot 3^{(i-1)}-3+1)/2 \\ &= 3^{(i-1)}(L_{n-i+2}+L_{n-i+1}+1)+2 \cdot 3^{(i-1)}-1 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, eq. (10) is proven to be correct.

Proposition 4.

In case that a given a positive integer N is expressed in the binary remainder representation as follows:

$$N = 2L_n + K_n$$

$$L_n = 2L_{n-1} + K_{n-1}$$

$$L_{n-1} = 2L_{n-2} + K_{n-2}$$

$$\vdots$$

$$L_1 = 2L_0 + K_0,$$

and when the following condition is given for the remainder K_i ,

$$K_i = 1, \text{ for } n-p+1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$K_{n-p} = 0,$$

$$K_i = \{1, 0\}, \text{ for } 0 \leq i \leq n-p-1,$$

p times consecutive Collatz operations on N always gives an even number.

That is,

$$C^{p+1}(N) = C(C^p(N)) = C^p(N)/2.$$

Proof. According to Proposition 3, under the condition that $K_i = 1$, for $n-p+1 \leq i \leq n$, $C^{p-1}(N)$ is expressed as follows.

$$C^{p-1}(N) = 3^{(p-2)} \cdot (L_{n-p+3} + L_{n-p+2}) + 2 \cdot 3^{(p-2)} - 1.$$

Here, with assuming $K_{n-p} = 0$, we calculate $C^p(N)$.

$$\begin{aligned} C(C^{p-1}(N)) &= C^p(N) \\ &= (3(3^{(p-2)} \cdot (L_{n-p+3} + L_{n-p+2}) + 2 \cdot 3^{(p-2)} - 1) + 1) / 2 \\ &= (3^{(p-1)} \cdot (L_{n-p+3} + L_{n-p+2}) + 2 \cdot 3^{(p-1)} - 2) / 2 \\ &= (3^{(p-1)} \cdot (2L_{n-p+2} + 1 + 2L_{n-p+1} + 1) + 2 \cdot 3^{(p-1)} - 2) / 2 \\ &= 3^{(p-1)} \cdot (L_{n-p+2} + L_{n-p+1} + 1) + 3^{(p-1)} - 1 \\ &= 3^{(p-1)} \cdot (2L_{n-p+1} + 1 + L_{n-p+1} + 1) + 3^{(p-1)} - 1 \\ &= 3^{(p-1)} \cdot (3L_{n-p+1} + 3) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&=3^p \cdot (L_{n-p+1}+1)-1 \\
&=3^p \cdot (2L_{n-p}+1)-1
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

The parity of eq. (13) does not depend on p and L_{n-p} , and is always even.

Proposition 5.

In case that a given positive integer N is expressed in the binary remainder representation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
N &= 2L_n + K_n \\
L_n &= 2L_{n-1} + K_{n-1} \\
L_{n-1} &= 2L_{n-2} + K_{n-2} \\
&\vdots \\
L_1 &= 2L_0 + K_0,
\end{aligned}$$

and when the following condition is given for the remainder K_i ,

$$\begin{aligned}
K_i &= 1, \text{ for } n-p+1 \leq i \leq n, \\
K_{n-p} &= 0, \\
K_i &= \{1, 0\}, \text{ } 0 \leq i \leq n-p-1,
\end{aligned}$$

that is, when K_i first becomes 0 at K_{n-p} . In this case, according to Proposition 4,

$$C^{p+1}(N) = C^p(N)/2 = M.$$

Here, the parity of M (even or odd) depends on K_{n-p-1} and p .

Proof. Under the given condition on K_i , from eq. (13),

$$C^p(N) = 3^p \cdot (2L_{n-p} + 1) - 1.$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
C^{p+1}(N) &= C^p(N)/2 \\
&= 3^p \cdot L_{n-p} + (3^p - 1)/2 \\
&= 3^p(2L_{n-p-1} + K_{n-p-1}) + (3^p - 1)/2 \\
&= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + 3^p \cdot K_{n-p-1} + (3^p - 1)/2.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{If } K_{n-p-1} = 1, \quad C^{p+1}(N) = 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^p - 1)/2. \tag{14}$$

$$\text{If } K_{n-p-1}=0, \quad C^{p+1}(N)=2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1}+(3^{p+1}-1)/2. \quad (15)$$

The parity of $C^{p+1}(N)$ in eqs. (14) and (15) depends only on p in the second term of both equations. We examine the parity of $C^{p+1}(N)$ in the following four cases.

Case A: $K_{n-p-1}=0, \quad p=2p'+1$

$$\begin{aligned} C^{p+1}(N) &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^p - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{(2p'+1)} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3(3^{2p'} - 1) + 2)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + 3(3^{p'} + 1)(3^{p'} - 1)/2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Here, both $(3p'+1)$ and $(3p'-1)$ are even numbers. Therefore, $3(3p'+1)(3p'-1)/2$ gives an even number. As a result, in this case, $C^{p+1}(N)$ gives an odd number.

Case B: $K_{n-p-1}=0, \quad p=2p'$

$$\begin{aligned} C^{p+1}(N) &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{2p'} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{p'} + 1)(3^{p'} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2X_B \\ &= \text{'even'} \end{aligned}$$

Case C: $K_{n-p-1}=1, \quad p=2p'+1$

$$\begin{aligned} C^{p+1}(N) &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{p+1} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{(2p'+2)} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{p'+1} + 1)(3^{p'+1} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2X_C \\ &= \text{'even'} \end{aligned}$$

Case D: $K_{n-p-1}=1, \quad p=2p'$

$$\begin{aligned} C^{p+1}(N) &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{p+1} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3^{2p'+1} - 1)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + (3(3^{2p'} - 1) + 2)/2 \\ &= 2 \cdot 3^p \cdot L_{n-p-1} + 3(3^{p'} + 1)(3^{p'} - 1)/2 + 1 \\ &= 2X_D + 1 \end{aligned}$$

= 'odd'

Therefore, the parity of $C^{p+1}(N)$ can be summarized as follows.

$$K_{n-p-1}=0, p=0, \text{ then } C^{p+1}(N)=0,$$

$$K_{n-p-1}=0, p=1, \text{ then } C^{p+1}(N)=1,$$

$$K_{n-p-1}=1, p=0, \text{ then } C^{p+1}(N)=1,$$

$$K_{n-p-1}=1, p=1, \text{ then } C^{p+1}(N)=0,$$

here, even and odd numbers are represented using the modulo 2 notation. That is, even numbers are 0, and odd numbers are 1.

As shown in the Supplementary Information at the end of this paper, the Collatz operation sequence turns out to be closely related to the binary remainder representation of the integers given initially. In the following propositions, it is shown that any Collatz operation sequence has a common subsequence with any other Collatz operation sequences.

Proposition 6.

A number sequence $S(N_1)$ is defined as that is generated by repeated Collatz operations on an arbitrary positive integer N_1 . $S(N_1)$ always contains a subsequence of a sequence $S(N_2)$ which is generated by repeated Collatz operations on an integer N_2 that is not included in $S(N_1)$.

Proof. The Collatz sequence generated from an arbitrary integer N_1 is represented as follows.

$$S(N_1): C(N_1), C^2(N_1), C^3(N_1) \cdot \cdot \cdot C^i(N_1) \cdot \cdot \cdot ,$$

From $S(N_1)$, we can always select $C^i(N_1)$ which is an odd number. If N_1 is a power of two, we exclude it. The reason is that if N_1 is a power of 2, the Collatz sequence becomes trivial.

If $C^i(N_1)=q$, and q is an odd number, then,

$$C^{i+1}(N_1)=(3q+1)/2.$$

Next, let's assume that a certain odd number r satisfies the following equation.

$$4^t \cdot C^{i+1}(N_1) = 4^t \cdot (3q+1)/2 = (3r+1)/2 = C(r) \quad (16)$$

where, t is an arbitrary positive integer.

$C(r)$ is not included in the sequence $S(N_1)$. If $C(r)$ were included in $S(N_1)$, then $C(r)$ would be expressed by the following equation, where m is a positive integer.

$$C^{i+1+m}(N_1) = C(r) \quad (17)$$

On the other hand, eq. (18) can be derived according to eqs. (16) and (1).

$$C^{2t+1}(r) = C^{i+1}(N_1) \quad (18)$$

Then, the following equation is obtained from eqs. (17) and (18).

$$C^{2^{t+1+m}}(r)=C(r) \quad (19)$$

Equation (19) is contradicted by Proposition 1. Therefore, $C(r)$ is not included in the Collatz sequence $S(N_1)$.

Next, we clarify the relationship between q and r , that is, even if we select odd number q from $S(N_1)$ arbitrary, r that satisfies equation (16) always exists. Equation (20) is obtained from eq. (16).

$$4^t \cdot (3q+1)=(3r+1) \quad (20)$$

When $t=1$, equation (20) indicates $r=4q+1$. Therefore, a positive integer r that meets eq. (16) always exists. Similarly, if $t=2$, $r=16q+5$.

Next, it is shown that eq. (20) has integer solutions when t is any integer. By transforming eq. (20), we obtain the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned} r &= 4^t q + (4^t - 1) / 3 \\ &= 4^t q + (2^{2t} - 1) / 3 \\ &= 4^t q + (2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

As is well known, the second term of eq. (21) always becomes a multiple of 3. This is because three consecutive integers $(2^t - 1)$, 2^t , and $(2^t + 1)$ must include a multiple of 3, and since 2^t cannot be a multiple of 3, either $(2^t + 1)$ or $(2^t - 1)$ must be a multiple of 3. Therefore, it has been shown that r always has integer solutions.

Next, we verify that r is contained in a Collatz sequence $S(N_2)$ that is different from $S(N_1)$. For this verification, it is sufficient to show that there always exists an integer M that satisfies equation (22).

$$C(M) = 4^t q + (2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3 \quad (22)$$

Here, if M is set an odd number as $M=2b+1$, then equation (23) is obtained.

$$(3(2b+1)+1)/2 = 2^{2t} q + (2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3 \quad (23)$$

Transforming equation (23) gives equation (24).

$$3b+2 = 2^{2t} q + (2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3 = 2^{2t} q + t', \quad (24)$$

where,

$$t' = (2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3. \quad (25)$$

In case that $2^{2t} q + t'$ is set as $3q'+2$, $b = q'$ and $M = 2q'+1$.

However, when $2^{2t} q + t' = 3q'+1$, there is no integer solution for b . In that case, we need to prove the existence of an integer M' that meets $C(M') = 2r$, that is,

$$C(M') = 2 \{ 4^t q + (2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3 \}$$

Here, as in equation (25), we set $(2^t + 1)(2^t - 1) / 3 = t'$ and set $M' = 2b'+1$, we obtain equation (26).

$$3b'+2 = 2(2^{2t} q + t') \quad (26)$$

In equation (26), we again can set $2^{2t}q+t'=3q'+1$, then we obtain $b'=2q'$, that is, $M'=4q'+1$. As shown in following Proposition 7, multiples of 3 do not appear in the Collatz sequence basically. Therefore, the case that $2^{2t}q+t'=3q'$, that is, $C(M)$ is a multiple of 3 is not needed to consider.

Above considerations can be summarized as follows. If an arbitrary odd number q is selected from the Collatz operation sequence $S(N_1)$, the integer r is calculated using equation (21), then equation (27) holds.

$$C^{2t+1}(r)=C^{i+1}(N_1) \quad (27)$$

Further, it has been shown that r is not included in $S(N_1)$, and that there always exist M and M' such that $C(M) = r$ or $C(M') = 2r$, as well. This fact shows that the integer r is included in a Collatz operation sequence $S(N_2)$ that is different from $S(N_1)$. In equation (27), we can set $2t+1=j$, then,

$$C^j(r)=C^{i+1}(N).$$

Therefore,

$$C^{j+m}(r)=C^{i+1+m}(N), \quad \text{for } m \geq 0.$$

Above conclusion indicates that any Collatz sequence $S(N_1)$ shares a subsequence with another Collatz sequence $S(N_2)$ at least.

Proposition 7.

Multiples of 3 do not appear basically in a Collatz sequence generated from an arbitrary integer N . Multiples of 3 appear in a Collatz sequence only when an initially given integer N satisfies the condition indicated in eq. (28), and even in this case, multiples of 3 disappear from the Collatz sequence after repeating the Collatz operation for n times.

$$N=2^n 3 \cdot m \quad \text{for } n \geq 1, \quad m \geq 1. \quad (28)$$

Proof. If N is an odd number and $C(N)$ is a multiple of 3, then it is necessary that eq. (29) holds true.

$$C(N)=(3N+1)/2=3p, \quad \text{where } p \text{ is a positive integer, then,}$$

$$3(2p-N)=1. \quad (29)$$

However, there are no integers p and N that satisfy eq. (29).

On the other hand, if N is an even number and $C(N)$ is a multiple of 3, then,

$$C(N)=N/2=3p.$$

With Generalizing, we obtain the following equation.

$$C^i(N)=N/2^i=3p, \quad \text{then,}$$

$$N=2^i \cdot 3p$$

Next, when we carry out Collatz operation on N , then we obtain equation (30).

$$C(C^i(N))=(3 \cdot 3p+1)/2=(9p+1)/2=3p'$$

$$3(2p'-3p)=1 \tag{30}$$

There are no integers p and p' that satisfy eq. (30). Hence, the Collatz sequence generated from an arbitrary integer N does not contain multiples of 3 basically.

Proposition 8.

There is no Collatz sequence that does not share a common sequence with any other Collatz sequence.

Proof. Choose any odd number N , and consider the Collatz operation sequence $S(N)$ and the set of all Collatz operation sequences that share a common subsequence with $S(N)$. According to Proposition 7, we can exclude multiples of 3 from the Collatz operation sequences. For example, when we consider the integers from 2 to 12, we find each integer is included in at least one Collatz operation sequence as follows.

- 2: $C(1)$,
- 3: excluded due to a multiple of 3,
- 4: $C^2(5)$,
- 5: $(4q+1)$, see proposition 6, $q=1$ and $t=1$ in equation (20),
- 6: excluded due to a multiple of 3,
- 7: $C^6(149)$,
- 8: $C(5)$,
- 9: excluded due to a multiple of 3,
- 10: $C^2(13)$,
- 11: $C(7)$,
- 12: excluded due to a multiple of 3.

Therefore, according to Proposition 6, all the above Collatz operation sequences must have a common subsequence. In fact, the following relationship holds.

$$C(4)=C^3(5)=C^{10}(7)=C^2(8)=C^4(10)=C^9(11)=2$$

Next, we choose an arbitrary integer n and perform the same verification with a sequence of 12 integers starting from $12n+1$.

- $12n+1$: $(4q+1)$, see proposition 6, $q=3n$ and $t=1$ in equation (20),
- $12n+2$: $C(8n+1)$,
- $12n+3$: excluded due to a multiple of 3,
- $12n+4$: $C^2(16n+5)$,
- $12n+5$: $(4q+1)$, see proposition 6, $q=3n+1$ and $t=1$ in equation (20),
- $12n+6$: excluded due to a multiple of 3,
- $12n+7$: $C^2(16n+9)$,
- $12n+8$: $C(8n+5)$,
- $12n+9$: excluded due to a multiple of 3,
- $12n+10$: $C^2(16n+13)$,
- $12n+11$: $C(8n+7)$,
- $12n+12$: excluded due to a multiple of 3.

Since n is selected from any integers, the integers $12n+i$, where $1 \leq i \leq 12$, covers all integers. Above consideration concludes that the Collatz operation sequence $S(N)$ generated from any odd number N , and all Collatz sequences that share a common subsequence with $S(N)$, together encompass all integers. Hence, it is concluded that there are no Collatz operation sequences that do not share a common sequence with $S(N)$.

Proposition 9.

Repeated Collatz operations on any positive integer always result in 1.

Proof. From equation (20) in proposition 6, in order for any given Collatz sequence to have a common subsequence with another Collatz sequence, it is essential that at least one of the sequences contains two consecutive even numbers. This condition is guaranteed by the conclusions of Propositions 4 and 5. Proposition 2 is important as well. Proposition 2 indicates the fact that at least one of K_i in the binary remainder representation always keeps “0” in the repeated Collatz operations. Furthermore, Propositions 6 and 8 show that all Collatz operation sequences have a common subsequence. Therefore, if we select any two Collatz sequences S_1 and S_2 , a common subsequence S_3 is automatically determined. That is,

$$S_3 = S_1 \cap S_2.$$

Further, S_3 also has a common subsequence with another arbitrary Collatz sequences S_4 as follows.

$$S_5 = S_4 \cap (S_1 \cap S_2)$$

Even beyond S_5 , the common subsequence continues to form further common subsequences with other Collatz sequences. As shown in Proposition 6, the beginning of common subsequence of Collatz operation sequences is basically delayed when it merges with another Collatz operation sequence. In other words, the index m of the starting term $C^{i+m}(N)$ of the common subsequence increases according to increase of number of converged Collatz operation sequences. Finally, the common subsequence that all Collatz operation sequences share shrinks to the ultimate common subsequence represented below.

$$8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1. \tag{31}$$

According to Propositions 6 and 8, another simple proof is possible.

Here, N_1 , N_2 , and N_3 are arbitrarily chosen integers. If you actually perform the calculations, you will find that the Collatz operation sequences, $S(N_1)$, $S(N_2)$, and $S(N_3)$ have the common subsequence shown in eq. (31). At this time, the integer 8 is the only integer to start this subsequence, and it is not possible to reach 4 or 2 directly from any other integers through the Collatz operation. Therefore, according to Propositions 6 and 8, the sequence shown in eq. (31) should be the ultimate common subsequence shared by all the Collatz operation sequences.

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【Supplementary Information】

An example of a Collatz operation sequence is shown in Table 1. In this example, the initially given number N is 127, and the results of each Collatz operation $C^R(127)$ are shown in the second column of the table, and the parities of the each operation results is shown in the third column as "0" = even and "1" = odd. The fourth and subsequent columns in the table show L_n and K_n of the binary remainder representation of the individual results of Collatz operation. It is worth noting that there is a strong correlation between K_n in the binary remainder representation and the parities of the Collatz operation results. For example, the sequence of K_n highlighted in yellow is exactly the same as parities of the Collatz operation sequence highlighted in yellow, where the occurrence of even number at $R = 7$ is explained in accordance with Proposition 4. Furthermore, in the sequence of numbers highlighted in blue, the occurrence of even and odd numbers follows Proposition 5. Even from this simple example, we can see that the Collatz operation sequence is deterministically generated based on the binary remainder representation of the initial given number N .

